

Research

Internet service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty assessment in Burundian banking industry

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Abstract: The objective of this study is to examine web benefit quality in Burundi and analyse its effect on client fulfilment. The thought of working on this specific venture came from the reality that web managing an account is not so prevalent to Burundian clients, but moreover it comprises a segment which appears incredible advancement in Africa and tends to induce more far reaching within the following few a long time. It is genuine that within the close future, exchanges and other keeping money activities will get accessory for the most part through web. This has too made the clients well mindful of the benefit level accessible around the world and hence anticipates the leading from his bank. In this advanced client-centric competitive field, fulfilment and quality demonstrate to be key components and are interrelated. To endeavour in a market characterized by worldwide competition, and mechanical progressions, banks must be more customer focused. Useful challenging methods have been used to get 125 respondents from customer of banking services in different banks within Bujumbura city. Data was processed using a quantitative technique and was gathered through the use of a well-structured questionnaire. After that, the data was examined employing SmartPLS 3.0 and SPSS V.26 software. The outcomes revealed that, in general, the quality of e-services offered by Burundian banking sector does not meet customer expectations.

Keywords: Burundi, Internet Banking, Service quality, Customer satisfaction, Customer loyalty

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Introduction

Service quality and client fulfilment have long been recognized as playing significant part in victory and survival in today's competitive showcase. Service quality could be later conclusive issue within the showcasing thought. It moreover makes a difference control the competitive position, and thus, decides the advertise share and benefits. The banking industry in Burundi has seen a few changes all through the most recent decade with the approach of private

segment banks and public banks. Within the current hard-hitting money related condition of banks, client devotion has turned out to be impressively more essential to hold the extraordinary client and suitable treatment of clients turns out to be much more basic to commerce accomplishment.

According to the latest survey conducted by the Central Bank of Burundi (BRB) in 2016, on financial inclusion, the financial and Burundian banking system has very limited penetration of banking services. In this 2016 survey, the penetration rate of the Bank of the Republic of Burundi was about 22%. Some local commercial banks have branches in the city centre. Microfinance institutions mainly serve rural areas. The Burundi government is a minority shareholder of three main banks which are BANCOBU (Commercial Bank of Burundi), BCB (Bujumbura Credit Bank), and IBB (Interbank Burundi). These banks are the three public banks with more than 2/3 of the market share. The soundness of the banking sector has improved, the ratio of capitalization to liquidity has exceeded regulatory standards, and profitability indicators have risen. However, the quality of bank's portfolio remains an issue, as the non-performing loans (NPLs) share reaches 6% and the East Africa Community states reference rate is 5%. The industry also suffered from a shortfall in foreign exchange after the Central Bank implemented de facto capital controls in 2019.

The Burundian financial sector consists of 14 financial institutions (banks), including the New Youth Investment Bank and Agriculture Bank, 40 microfinance institutions, 16 insurance companies, 3 social security institutions and 3 payment institutions. Banks for women have also been established. The Central Bank Controls banking oversight policies, including measures for the health of banking system.

Loyalty is made over time outline from an unsurprising record of get-togethers and regardless outperforming client wants in any bank. The private banks and public banks draw in clients with their varied quality administrations and quality related with the client that set up client fulfilment and client devotion. It is essentially vital for banks to preserve profitable customers and to reinforce the return from the existing customer base to supply careful thought to the issues of customer loyalty improving. Service quality is characterized as fluctuation between customer desire of service and customer's recognitions of the real benefit. The Internet is the driving force behind the growth of e-commerce [1]. In today's business environment, data and communication applications are critical concerns for banks, and the web has evolved into the primary stage for all money-related transactions, keeping money and commercial transactions on display.

The employment of quality and excellent service is very important to gratify their customers and, in another way, to maintain their loyalty. Therefore, it wants supplementary examines and this paper aims to fill this gap by endeavouring to address the link between service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction for nourishing loyal customer.

Literature review

1. Quality

Quality was defined from various points of view. The ability to meet needs is what quality is all about. The degree to which a product fits the needs of a certain consumer is referred to as quality. Every facet of a product, including the services included in the sales contract, has an impact on the demand curve, and quality is one of them. The degree to which an item (a combination of product, model) possesses the service attributes that you desire is referred to as quality. A product's quality is determined by how well it conforms to consumer preferences. Quality is defined as the level of excellence at an affordable amount and the mastery of variability at an affordable price,[2]. Quality is determined by the purchaser. Compliance with company conditions is not quality; according to customer conditions is.[3].

2. Service quality

Overtime, service quality can be assessed by observing the match between expectations about the performance of service received by customers, or the performance of service provided by the company, seen from direct evaluations provided by customers. [4].

3. Service quality dimensions

It was explicitly noted that service quality research in banking industry can be divided into three subject areas: proponents of SERVQUAL, proponents of modified SERVIQUAL, and proponents of new models. The empirically validated model of Parasuraman et al. (1988) suggests that service quality is a multi-dimensional construct that suggests five dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Furthermore, The SERVQUAL methodology has been used in a number of studies to assess bank service quality [5].

Tangibles (TG): physical structure, kit, and appearance of staffs

Reliability (RL): the capability to execute the assured service reliably and truthfully

Responsiveness (RE): readiness to support clients as well as providing fast service.

Assurance (ASS): Employee acquaintance and courtesy, as well as their ability to generate trust and security (including aptitude, trustworthiness, and safety).

Empathy: Individual care and attention that the company delivers to its clients (including access, communication, and customer comprehension) [6].

4. Service quality and customer satisfaction

Nowadays, service providers and service marketers prioritize and focus their consideration on building and delivering quality services. That's why it's so important to create a competitive environment for organizations to sustain. Specific evidence shows that organizations can increase sales, revenue and improve the value of organizations while focusing their activities on customer satisfaction through quality services. Good customer satisfaction will be a great way to promote yourself, especially by providing good information through word of mouth about customers services, by increasing resale and attracting new customers [7]. Hence, the quality of service perceived by suppliers may not always be the same as customer point of view. [8].

5. Service quality and customer loyalty

Customer loyalty refers to the degree to which buyers get devoted up to a specific brand, products or services over time [9]. It reflects the ratio of customers who are satisfied with the service provided by a service supplier. Loyalty behaviors reflect a consumer's willingness to tell others about how pleased they are with the service they have received, who may also be clients of their friends' preferred company provider. There is also the hope that loyal customers will refer friends and family to their services. Customers are also encouraged to prioritize their brand in all aspects of the banking business. On the other hand, loyal behavior encourages consumers to return to a service provider year after year.

As a result, researchers concentrated on the hotel industry, and authors performed a study to investigate the role of trade-offs for hotel owners. In hotels, business owners must pick between service quality innovation and client loyalty. The reporters collected information from hotel customers of Pakistan's major cities, 362 questionnaires were used.

The structural equation modeling method was used to investigate the positive interactions between innovation in good service and customer loyalty in hotels for business owners.

According to the findings, the role of customer satisfaction as a mediator and the role of estimating the value of an order in the market between quality of service and customer loyalty is significant. Furthermore, the authors stated that the study's findings can be used by restaurant owners to improve customer loyalty by emphasizing satisfaction and product cost [10].

Several studies on service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty have been conducted by various authors. Once more, the one conducted by [11], The partial least squares method (PLS-SEM) was used to study 430 Egyptian internet users to determine the relationship between service recovery strategy, service recovery satisfaction, and two types of customer loyalty to ISP. Through service recovery satisfaction, the study helped to understand how the seven service recovery strategies directly and indirectly affect customer loyalty, attitudes, and behaviours. The authors clarified that their findings are useful to service managers dealing with denial of service as well as academics interested in how service providers respond to service disruptions and customer complaints in a B2C context. The study's findings revealed that certain SR strategies have a positive effect on both service recovery satisfaction and customer loyalty to ISPs. Furthermore, satisfaction with service restoration has a positive impact.

Methodology

1. Study design, population, and sampling method

A quantitative approach was utilized to process findings, data was gathered using a structured questionnaire, then it was assessed by the help of SmartPLS 3.0 and SPSS V.26 analysis tools.

This study used a snowball sampling method, which is the more well-known forms of non-probability method. This is especially well-suited for cases where it is difficult to reach the target population and it is difficult for researchers to create a population list and my subject of research is one of these cases mentioned. Snowball sampling is one of the most widely used sampling method in both quantitative and qualitative research, with a focus on network and transfer characteristics. Researchers typically begin with a small number of initial contacts, appropriate to the research situation and are invited to participants in the study. Voluntary participants are then asked to recommend other participants who meet the research guidelines and likely to be participants, and then to recommend other potential participants etc.[12]. Moreover, as there are different types of snowball sampling, this study particularly used Exponential Non-Discriminative Snowball Sampling, where each participant involved in the research work will recruit another participant [13]. The study used the maximum of 125 respondents taken from 150 participants as total sample size. The study performed by [14] presents a table and a formula for calculating sample lengths for a particular population with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, (0.05: the value of Z equal to 1.96). The sample size of a well-known populace can be determined by the following formula:

$$n = \frac{p(100-p)z^2}{E^2}$$

n is required sample size

P is the percentage occurrence of a state or condition

E is the percentage maximum error required

Z is the value corresponding to level of confidence

2. Data collection instrument

The tool used in this study is a questionnaire, it is designed based on five dimensions of quality of service, and 22 service elements of the SERVPERF modified model [15]. The study instrument has four parts including 34 questions, in the first part of the questionnaire, the author asked about sociodemographic profile of the willing respondents to take part in this study. It contained information such as age, gender, educational level, and their occupation.

The second part deals with questions used for an assessment of quality of services of the Burundian banking industry. The developed questionnaire, contained of four questions representing tangibles service quality extents, five inquiries that focusing on reliability aspects, five inquiries on responsiveness dimensions, four inquiries represent assurance dimensions, and four inquiries which focused on empathy. The third part is to measure customer satisfaction utilizing 4 items that assess the level of satisfaction with the e-service provided by Burundian banking sector. The last remaining segment is customer loyalty, and there are three queries modified from [16]. Researcher collected data from volunteer participants from Bujumbura, the Burundian economic capital city, in questionnaire sent to them, they have been asked to complete the questionnaire and return responses for data assessment.

The questionnaire that was sent to the respondents was translated in French language so that they can better understand the content of the questionnaire, as many Burundians are French speakers however some of them can also speak English.

On a 5-point Likert scale, respondents rated their consent to each request (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) or (1 = strongly dissatisfied to 5 = strongly satisfied).

The questionnaire's reliability and validity were tested using developed questions on internet service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty within the Burundian keeping money industry.

For such a study to be properly carried out, I had to formulate basic research hypotheses in the form of the provisional confirmation that these hypotheses will be confirmed or rejected after data analysis.

H1. There is a close relationship between the E-service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction in banking services.

H2. In banking E-services, there is a relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

H3. In banking E-services, there is relationship between E-service quality dimensions and customer loyalty.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

3. Data analysis

To analyse the collected data in accordance with the overall purpose of the research, statistical procedures were performed using SmartPLS 3.0 and SPSS v.26, in this section, to identify key issues and provide actionable recommendations for issues related to customer satisfaction and loyalty as a result of e-service quality. The survey consisted of 29 items. But only 24 were chosen and utilized throughout data analysis due to the validity of their load values based on the Cronbach's Alpha and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) results [17].

Results and Discussion

1. Reliability and Validity

Validity elucidates the extent to which the data collected covers the actual survey area [18]. Validity means “measure what is supposed to measure” [19]. There are numerous types of instrument validation, content validity, construct validity, and reliability were all used by the author in this study. The term "content validity" refers to "the extent to which the instrument will be generalized." [20]. In general, validation involves the evaluation of a new research tool to ensure that it includes the whole thing that is important and eliminates everything that is not needed in a particular item’s structural components. It is in this logic that all the items used in this study were firstly endorsed by expert in the academic area, and minor adjustments were proposed and made to the questionnaire.

2. Construct Reliability and validity

Conferring to [21] reliability’s model assessment, each indicator loading within its related latent variables, need to be calculated at any cost then will be compared to a threshold. Furthermore, for [22] the loadings output for the model should remain higher than 0.70 within the corresponding indicators reliability, composite reliability in order to be considered adequate. Within our study, all and each composite reliability value stood consistent with such assumption and have been loaded higher than 0.70 as the indorsed value. The remaining lowest value for our situation was 0.917 while the highest one was 0.964. In agreement with [23], if the value of AVE is greater than 0.50, the items assessing and measuring the variable can be considered to be valid and reliable. Cronbach's Alpha values were far above the 0.6 threshold. In addition, the value of rho_A was used to assess construct reliability, and it must be greater than 0.70 to establish inner consistency. According to the study's findings, all research variable loadings values were significantly higher than 0.70. As a result, these findings indicate that the measurement model and computations were reliable. The table below reproduces Cronbach's Alpha, rho_A, Composite reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values

Table 1: Reliability and validity

	Cronbach’s Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CL	0.879	0.880	0.926	0.806
CS	0.818	0.819	0.917	0.846
E-SQD	0.960	0.962	0.964	0.585

3. Discriminant reliability

To evaluate the potential level of each variable, to corroborate that it is different from other construct, Fornell-Larcker criterion have been utilized for verification and validation of discriminant validity [24].

Table 2: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	CL	CS	E-SQD
CL	0.898		
CS	0.765	0.920	
E-SQD	0.818	0.752	0.765

As well, the wholly diagonal values should be greater than non-diagonal values, the results in the table above demonstrate that all diagonal values are bigger than non-diagonal values which means that no issue is found in the model related to the discriminant validity.

The Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio was also calculated as a better method of determining discriminant validity.

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio

		CL	CS	E-SQD
	CL			
	CS	0,900		
	E-SQD	0,886	0,854	

HTMT values must load between 0.85 to 0.90 to be considered acceptable and suitable to establish discriminant validity. As can be seen in the table overmentioned, the outcomes are as follows: All the values loaded above the threshold which means that, there is no issues about the discriminant validity within the model [25].

4. Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

Outer VIF values and Inner VIF values were also calculated to assess and check the multicollinearity issues may occur in the model. Results are presented in the tables two below respectively.

Table 4: Outer VIF value

Indicators	VIF
ASS2	3,449
ASS3	3,004
ASS4	2,900
CL1	2,174
CL2	2,750
CL3	2,535
CS3	1,923
CS4	1,923
EM3	2,493
EM4	3,731
RE1	4,162
RE2	3,192
RE3	3,755
RE4	2,481
RE5	2,961
RL1	3,178
RL2	2,664
RL3	3,114
RL4	3,485
RL5	4,060
TG1	3,772

TG2	2,675
TG3	1,994
TG4	2,393

Table 5: Inner VIF values

	CL	CS	E-SQD
CL			
CS	2,301		
E-SQD	2,301	1,000	

Both the Outer VIF and the Inner VIF are less than 5. As a result, it's established that the variables don't have any issues with multicollinearity. When the Inner and Outer VIF values are both more than 5, multicollinearity is present, and those elements must be deleted, which is not the case in our model [17].

5. Demographic characteristics of the respondents

In this study, 77 out of 125 respondents were male, represented (61.6%); while 48 respondents were female (38.4%). Among our respondents, 48 (38.4%) were aged between 18-30 years old while 56 respondents (44.8%) were aged between 31-40 years old. 21 (16.8%) respondents were aged between 41-50 years old. Educational level of the respondents within this study were as follow; respondents who have completed the secondary school were 4 (3.2%) out of 125 total respondents. University; 67 respondents, (53.6%), Master’s degree, 43 respondents (34.4%), while for Ph.D. we had only 11 respondents (8.8%).

Table 6: E-service quality dimensions, Scores Mean and Standards Deviation

Descriptive Statistics					
Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
TG1	125	1	5	3,35	1,034
TG2	125	1	5	3,31	1,011
TG3	125	1	5	3,32	0,955
TG4	125	1	5	3,24	1,003
RL1	125	1	5	3,04	1,027
RL2	125	1	5	2,97	1,031
RL3	125	1	5	3,01	0,996
RL4	125	1	5	2,85	1,100
RL5	125	1	5	2,96	1,103
RE1	125	1	5	2,98	1,062
RE2	125	1	5	2,98	1,039
RE3	125	1	5	2,71	1,176
RE4	125	1	5	2,91	0,925
RE5	125	1	5	3,10	1,110
ASS1	125	1	5	3,23	1,033
ASS2	125	1	5	3,26	1,071
ASS3	125	1	5	3,32	1,044

ASS4	125	1	5	3,36	0,919
EM1	125	1	5	2,61	1,325
EM2	125	1	5	2,82	1,212
EM3	125	1	5	2,94	1,030
EM4	125	1	5	3,05	1,084

Table 7: E-SQD overall Scores Mean and Std. Deviation

E-SQD	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tangibles	3.30	1.000
Reliability	2.96	1.051
Responsiveness	2.93	1.062
Assurance	3.29	1.016
Empathy	2.85	1.162

Descriptive statistics for tangibles (TG) revealed an overall mean score of 3.30 (SD = 1.000), the mean of tangibles is higher than 3, indicated neutral in the questionnaire, customer have been neutral in indicating their opinion-based tangibles. Reliability overall mean score was 2.96 (SD = 1.051) which meant that customer disagreed about reliability related services offered by different selected banks in Bujumbura. There was low interchangeability among responses according to the corresponding Std. Deviation. The banks leaders would more focus on the reliability related services. By the same token, responsiveness mean score revealed was 2.93 (SD = 1.062), this mean is low which means that respondents disagreed with the responsiveness services related. Banks need to focus on the section. The corresponding Std. Deviation was high which means that there was an insignificant responses' variation. The value of the overall mean score for assurance is 3.29, (SD = 1.016). This overall mean shows that in Burundian banking sector, clients disagreed with the way online services are conducted. Empathy has a mean score of 2.85 (SD = 1.162), the mean of the empathy is low which shows that somehow customers disagreed within the banking services empathy related.

Table 8: Customer satisfaction Scores Mean and Standards Deviation

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CS1	125	1	5	3,07	1,137
CS2	125	1	5	3,07	1,009
CS3	125	1	5	2,46	1,305
CS4	125	1	5	3,20	0,967

Table 9: Customer loyalty Scores Mean and Standards Deviation

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CL1	125	1	5	3,32	1,036
CL2	125	1	5	3,38	1,052
CL3	125	1	5	3,34	1,062

Table 10: Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty overall scores Mean and Standards Deviation

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customer satisfaction	2.95	1.104
Customer loyalty	3.34	1.050

Descriptive statistics for customer satisfaction (CS) revealed an overall mean score of 2.95 (SD = 1.104), it shows that Burundian banking customers were not satisfied about the e-services they been received so far, from their respective banks. Loyalty mean is 3.34, (SD = 1.050). The value of the loyalty score mean show that a huge number of the respondents didn't have the intention to continue being customers of their respective primary banks for a long time. It also showed that most of the respondents didn't have the inspiration to encourage their friends and relatives to keep on using the service delivered by the bank. The value of standard deviation is less which means that there is a low variability among the responses.

6. Testing study hypothesis

6.1. Bootstrapping, using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the hypothesis by way of Path Coefficients

Bootstrapping is a well-known technique for assessing, testing, and validating the model's significance. The path coefficients are replicated by the T-statistics value significance [26].

Table 11: Path Coefficients

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Hypothesis
E-SQD -> CS	0,752	0,761	0,047	16,140	0,000	Supported
CS -> CL	0,346	0,329	0,093	3,710	0,000	Supported
E-SQD -> CL	0,558	0,574	0,084	6,613	0,000	Supported

The outcomes of path coefficient demonstrate that the relationship between E-SQD → CS remains positive within original value of 0.752. The t-value corresponding to this relationship is 16.140 and it is more than 2. The p value for this relationship is 0.000, and it is less than 0.001 which means that it significant statistically. H1

Additionally, the path coefficients outcomes demonstrate that the relationship between CS → CL remain positive and within a Beta value of 3.346. For this relationship, the t-value is 3.710 which is greater than the threshold of 2. The P value is 0.000, which is less than 0.001 and indicates statistical significance. H2

Alike, the outcomes of path coefficient indicate that the relationship between E-SQD → CL is remaining significantly positive within a Beta value of 0.558. The t-value corresponding to this relationship is 6.613 greater than 2, the corresponding p value is 0.000, less than 0.001 as shown in table above and it is statistically significant. H3

6.2. Total effects and testing the research hypothesis

The outcomes of the bootstrapping are presented in the table below. According to the outcomes as demonstrated in the table below, total original effects, total mean effects, and all constructs were calculated to respond well to the model hypothesis. The standard deviation (STDEV), t-statistics, and p-value are all displayed in the same table. The results shown in the table reveals that the original and total mean values are both positive: E-SQD → CS, CS → CL and, E-SQD → CL. The results show that the relationship between E-SQD → CS is having a positive Original and Sample Mean, for this relationship, the Original is 0.752, its Mean value is 0.761, the t-value is 16.140 which is above 2, the required least level, within a p-value of 0.000 (statistically significant). H1

For CS → CL, Original is 0.346, for the same relationship, the mean value is 0.329 which all the values are positive within a t-value of 3.710 (greater than 2 the required minimum level) and a p-value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. H2

Furthermore, the relationship between E-SQD → CL, is having a positive original and Sample Mean as shown in the table below, its Original is 0.818, for this relationship, the mean value is 0.823, the t-value is 26.289 well above the mandatory minimum level of 2, within a statistically significant p-value of 0.000 less than 0.001. H3

Table 12: Total effects

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Decision
E-SQD -> CS	0,752	0,761	0,047	16,140	0,000	Supported
CS -> CL	0,346	0,329	0,093	3,710	0,000	Supported
E-SQD -> CL	0,818	0,823	0,031	26,289	0,000	Supported

The table above give us an overview of the results found and what we can retain from these results is that all the relationships tested, which are: E-SQD → CS, CS → CL, E-SQD → CL are positive and significant. With these results, we also found that the relationship between E-SQD → CS is positive and can be justified in the following way; if Burundian banks will be providing the good quality of e-services to their customers, this means that the level of customer satisfaction will also be increased in accordance with the level of the quality of the services offered. H1

Within the results, we can confirm that when the customer satisfaction is achieved, it will increase the customer loyalty. H2

Moreover, we can say that the relationship between E-SQD → CL is positive and significant. Thus, if the e-services offered by Burundian banks are the greatest, it means that the customers of these banks will be loyal to their respective banks. H3

6.3. Mediation Analysis

By doing the mediation analysis, specific indirect effects were computed. The outcomes are presented in the table below.

Table 13: Specific Indirect Effects

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
E-SQD -> CS -> CL	0,260	0,250	0,071	3,687	0,000

The results of the above table show that customer satisfaction (CS) mediates meaningfully between E-service quality dimensions (E-SQD) and customer loyalty (CL) within a significant p-value of 0.000 and t-statistics value 3.687, which is greater than the required minimum value of 2 ($3.687 > 2$). As a result, customer satisfaction (CS) is a powerful mediator between E-services quality dimensions (E-SQD) and customer loyalty (CL).

Conclusions

The study's main goal was to investigate the quality of internet service in Burundian banking sector and how it affects customer satisfaction and loyalty. To begin, the 24 items used in this survey are extremely valid and reliable in assessing service quality and its dimensions. In general, the quality of e-services offered by Burundian banking sector does not meet customer expectations. The research also attempted to investigate the link between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The highest and the lowest score mean values for service quality measurement range from 2.85 to 3.30. This shows that E-SQD should be carried out based on five service quality dimensions criteria measures. The highest mean score is 5 points, the overall values of service quality measurements results have fallen even below point 4 which means that banks in Burundian area need to focus more on offering adequate internet service quality to satisfy their customers as well to boost the customer loyalty since a satisfied customer is in many cases synonymous with a loyal customer. Furthermore, the study's findings revealed that all service quality measurements have a positive relationship with customer satisfaction and loyalty. Thus, it shows that the hypotheses proposed by the author are supported. Even though this study provides important information about the e-service quality in Burundian banking sector particularly in Bujumbura city, there is still room for expansion, explore for a deeper understanding of how e-banking services are provided in Burundi. Future research may highlight service quality across the banking sector throughout the territory of Burundi to get an overview of the quality of banking services within Burundian banking industry, especially e-services and this will allow the leaders of this sector to improve their services to increase customer satisfaction as well customer loyalty. A dissatisfied customer is too difficult to manage, the employees of these banks waste a lot of time on customer complaints, and this will disrupt almost the entire operation of the bank.

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